

SUSTAINABILITY MAPPING - Completing Exploratory Observations in Irish Women's Health Services: A Tool to Scope Opportunities for Responsible Design

Description:

This supplementary document includes higher resolution images of the sustainability mapping and outlines the groupings of consideration and opportunity statements in tables. These findings emerged from the final stage of analysis (Stage 3, Phase 3). Figure 1 displays the approach followed to identify opportunities and considerations for responsible design. It also highlights which part of the approach this supplementary information relates to.

Figure 1: Approach to Identification of Opportunities and Considerations for Responsible Design

‘Files’ refers to the number of contexts that had references categorised to each statement.

‘References’ refers to the number of individual raw data excerpts that were categorised to each statement.

‘Category’ refers to the group of considerations/opportunities the statements were categorized to.

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Table 1: Mapping of Consideration Statements

Consideration Statement	Files	References	Category
SOCIETY			
Considerations for clinicians comprehensively understanding their patient's case.	1	2	
Considerations for the personal preferences of patients regarding the provision of their care.	2	3	
Considerations for the need of a thorough patient history enquiry.	3	4	
Considerations for engaging partners and support personnel in care provision.	2	7	
Considerations for ensuring patient comfort by providing clear and detailed explanations of diagnoses.	4	24	
Considerations for staff limitations in disclosing information to patients.	1	1	
Considerations for the clinician's role in supporting patients to make informed decisions.	4	11	
Considerations for the emotional well-being of patients and their families.	2	5	
SOCIETY-ENVIRONMENT INTERSECTION			
Considerations for the clinician's role in supporting patients to make informed decisions.	4	11	
ENVIRONMENT-ECONOMY INTERSECTION			
Considerations for recognizing clinical setting limitations in service delivery.	2	5	
ECONOMY			
Considerations for test and procedure requirements in patient care.	2	2	
ECONOMY-SOCIETY INTERSECTION			
Considerations for differences in clinician skills and efficiency.	2	2	
Considerations for differences of opinion amongst clinicians.	1	1	
Considerations for adaptation time during transitions and change implementation.	1	1	
Considerations for adaptation time during transitions and change implementation.	1	1	
Considerations for managing audible distressing sounds in clinical settings.	3	5	
Considerations for the time required for medications to take effect.	1	2	

Considerations for ensuring patient comfort & privacy during medical examinations.	4	15	
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SOCIETY-ENVIRONMENT-ECONOMY INTERSECTION			
Considerations for aligning treatments and interventions with patient needs.	2	4	
Considerations for making an accurate and thorough diagnosis.	1	2	
Considerations for balancing enforcement of procedures with flexibility of guidelines.	1	1	
Considerations for constraints imposed by human resource limitations.	3	3	
Considerations for designing clinical settings with hygiene requirements in mind.	5	12	
Considerations for patients travelling to and from clinical settings.	3	5	
Considerations for the personal preferences of patients regarding the provision of their care.	2	3	

Mapping of Opportunity Statements

Figure 3: Mapped Opportunity Statements

Table 2: Mapping of Opportunity Statements

Opportunity Statement	Files	References	Category
SOCIETY			
Opportunity to optimize healthcare staff training and learning through collaborative and innovative approaches.	5	17	
Opportunity to improve the documentation of patient information for better continuity of care.	5	25	
Opportunity to optimize information flow between stakeholders.	7	43	
Opportunity to enhance patient preparedness ahead of their clinical appointment.	3	9	
Opportunity to enhance women's health expertise in primary care settings.	1	1	
Opportunity to ensure language barriers do not impact the quality of care provided.	2	3	
Opportunity to foster a diverse healthcare workforce that reflects the patient population.	2	5	
Opportunity to involve partners or support personnel in service provision.	2	7	
Opportunity to support patient comfort by addressing both physical and emotional well-being.	4	43	
Opportunity to design intuitive medical equipment that supports efficient adoption by healthcare staff.	1	1	
SOCIETY-ENVIRONMENT INTERSECTION			
Opportunity to minimize future medical interventions by focusing on education, early prevention and management.	5	11	
ENVIRONMENT			
Opportunity to explore efficient and sustainable uses of single-use materials in healthcare.	5	32	
Opportunity to optimize energy consumption whilst enhancing healthcare provision.	4	15	
Opportunity to optimize waste management systems in healthcare environments.	1	1	
ENVIRONMENT-ECONOMY INTERSECTION			
Opportunity to use piloting as a strategy to refine processes before wide-scale roll-out.	2	11	
ECONOMY			
Opportunity to minimize disruptive interruptions during clinical examinations.	1	5	
Opportunity to adopt and adapt successful processes and procedures in other contexts to enhance healthcare delivery.	4	10	

Opportunity to justify funding, scaling, and change within healthcare settings.	1	5	
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ECONOMY-SOCIETY INTERSECTION			
Opportunity to design healthcare systems that address disparities and prioritise equitable access and care.	2	5	
Opportunity to enhance collaboration and connectivity between public and private healthcare systems.	3	10	
Opportunity to optimize logistics relating to healthcare meetings and training sessions.	1	5	
Opportunity to optimize waiting lists and patient referral processes.	7	38	
Opportunity to streamline appointment scheduling to prevent delays and bottlenecks.	4	18	
Opportunity to streamline clinical appointments for an optimized patient and clinician experience.	7	61	
Opportunity to ensure accurate diagnosis and effective care planning.	2	7	
Opportunity to incorporate adjustability into medical furniture, equipment, and devices for enhanced patient and staff comfort.	1	3	
Opportunity to leverage collaboration for improved patient outcomes and healthcare system efficiency.	5	15	
Opportunity to strengthen the long-term reputation of service provision.	2	2	

SOCIETY-ENVIRONMENT-ECONOMY INTERSECTION			
Opportunity to educate patients and the wider community on health and wellness related topics.	2	8	
Opportunity to improve patient engagement with take-home materials, including thoughtful mementos and accessible information.	4	10	
Opportunity to address risk and fear of litigation amongst healthcare professionals.	1	1	
Opportunity to address healthcare professionals travelling between clinical settings.	1	2	
Opportunity to enhance patient autonomy and informed choice.	3	7	
Opportunity to evaluate change through comparative analysis.	2	8	
Opportunity to improve clinical setting layout and logistical efficiency.	5	54	